

Mediation of Work Engagement between Emotional Exhaustion, Cynicism and Turnover Intentions

Author's Detail: ¹Riaz Ahmed Mangi Assistant Professor Department of Commerce
Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur

²Prof: Dr Amanat Ali Jalbani Professor Faculty of Management Sciences
SZABIST Karachi

Abstract:

The research on occupational psychology has described that dimensions of burnout are significant predictor of turnover intentions among employees of services sector. However, the work engagement has negative impact on the turnover intentions. The study intends to investigate whether work engagement play mediating role between emotional exhaustion, cynicism and turnover intentions. The sample for current study was faculty members of higher education institutions in Sindh province of Pakistan. Barron and Kenny (1986) process was applied to test the mediation. All the variables were significantly correlated with each other. The mediation result shows that work engagement partially mediate between emotional exhaustion, cynicism and turnover intentions.

Keywords: Emotional Exhaustion, Cynicism, Work engagement, Turnover Intention, Mediation

I. Introduction

The past studies on occupational psychology has identified that level of burnout is the most significant predictor of turnover intention. The emerging research is describing that work engagement, considered as the opposite of burnout is the major predictor of retentions in organizations. The work engagement can reduce the impact of burnout and ultimately decrease the turnover intentions among employees. The studies in diverse organizations describe that there is negative relationship between work engagement and turnover intention of employees. "Work engagement has been linked to a decline in intentions to quit" (Koyuncu et al., 2006; Saks, 2006; Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004). According to the literature (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004), decreased work engagement could in turn lead to increased turnover intentions. "The link between work engagement, burnout and turnover intentions is empirically well established" (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004). Burnout has been found to contribute to the intent of employees to leave their organizations and it has been well documented by two Australian studies (Sims, 2007); the later study suggested cynicism and emotional exhaustion as

significant predictors of turnover intentions (Sims, 2007). Rothmann and Joubert (2007) reported similar findings in a South African study and Knudsen, Ducharme and Roman (2006) confirmed a positive link between emotional exhaustion and intentions to quit in a study conducted on a sample of therapeutic counselors. (Fogarty, Singh, Rhoads, and Moore, 2000; Huang, Chaung, and Lin, 2003). But no such study is found in literature that describes the mediation of work engagement between two dimensions of job burnout and turnover intentions. The currents study will fill this gap in the literature. The following mediation model is proposed for the study on the faculty of higher education institutions in Sindh. This study specifically focuses on the faculty of higher education institutions and particularly faculty of higher education institutions in Sindh to investigate the mediating role of work engagement between the dimension of burnout (emotional exhaustion, cynicism) and turnover intention.

II. Objectives and Significance

The main objective of the study is to comprehend the mediating effects of work engagement between two dimensions of burnout and turnover intentions among the faculty members of higher education

institutions. However, the correlation among dimensions of burnout and work engagement would also be calculated to understand the extent of relationship between two constructs. The current study would be unique in sense that the mediating role of work engagement between the two dimensions (emotional exhaustion, cynicism) of burnout and turnover intentions has not been tested in earlier studies on occupational psychology.

III. Literature Review

A. Work Engagement

Engagement viewed as highest level of devotion of the worker where the employee wishes to perform the job by applying his/her maximum capabilities for personal success and for the benefit of the organization. In 1993, Schmidt and colleagues introduced work engagement in the academic literature. In their opinion, engagement is the advanced and modern aspect of satisfaction at job. Schmidt and colleagues provided the one of the significant definition of engagement was that "a highly involved, strongly commitment and completely satisfaction with organizational objectives would be signified as engaged employee." Schmidt and colleagues integrated the classical aspect of job satisfaction developed by Smith (1969) and that of organizational commitment conceived by Allen and Mayers (1991). Though there are various definitions of work engagement but description of Schaufeli and Salanova (2002) regarding the work engagement is the most significant and popular. They defined work engagement as "positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is described by vigor, dedication, and absorption" (Schaufeli and Salanova, 2001). Numerous research scholars on occupational psychology in diverse organizational setting and environments have also studied the construct of work engagement. Hakanen (2006); Schaufeli, Martinez (2002) conducted studies in academic institutions, Schaufeli and Bakker (2004); Hallberg, Johansson, and Schaufeli (2007) in service sector. "It has been described in the occupational psychology literature that work engagement is opposite of the burnout and has been investigated and concluded in diverse organizational settings" (Schaufeli, Martinez, et al., 2002, Bakker, Demerouti, and Schaufeli, 2005, Hallberg, et al.,

2007). The work engagement is combination of three dimension e.g. vigor, dedication and absorption.

B. Emotional Exhaustion

The depletion of employee's emotional and mental stress that affects the psychological involvement in organization considered as emotional exhaustion. Maslach and Jackson (1981) defined emotional exhaustion in a sense that "workers feel they are no longer able to give themselves at a psychological level". The employee feel tired, fatigued their emotional energies are drained, when these feelings becomes chronic and long lasting, the workers are considered as emotionally exhausted. "The emotionally exhaustion normally experienced in human services organizations" (Maslach 1981, 1986). Gains and Germier (1983) defined this dimension of burnout in the personal toll perspective, in their opinion "emotional exhaustion is worker's reaction to stress and organizational pressure; lose feelings, concern, trust and interest in the performance to achieve organizational objectives" (Gains and Germier 1983). The organizational objectives badly suffer set backs due to emotional exhaustion because employee do not take expected interest and it becomes ever worse when the feelings become chronic. Besides MBI, the researchers and scholars have used other techniques and instruments to measure dimensions of burnout and came up with different interpretations. Demerouti and colleagues (2005) applied OLBI (Oldenburg Burnout Inventory) to measure the dimensions of burnout and concluded that prolong mental wear and tear as the exhaustion not emotional exhaustion, although the constructs are very similar. In 2005, a whole issue of work and Stress focused on this dimension of burnout. A large number of scholars in the issue of journal agreed and concluded that "emotional exhaustion is the integral dimension of burnout" (Halbesleben and Demerouti, 2005, Schaufeli and Taris, 2005). Kristensen and colleagues (2005) commented in the favor of emotional exhaustion as one factor construct of burnout. Demerouti (2004) applied Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI) to measure the burnout and used only one dimension, emotional exhaustion to assess the level of burnout among

employees. Besides Demerouti (2004), Bekker, Croon and Bressers (2005) who used only the items of emotional exhaustion from Maslach Burnout Inventory also adopted the one-dimensional approach of burnout.

C. Cynicism

The second dimension of burnout cynicism is the ensuing development of emotional exhaustion. Maslach and colleagues (2001) have described that the stress and burnout develop in a sequential method. The impact of one dimension of burnout results in the development of another dimension. Abraham (2000) and Albrecht (2002) defined that "cynicism as an emotional reaction to workers' doubts of organizational integrity". Demerouti (2002) described cynicism as disengagement from work, whereas, Maslach (2001) was of the firm opinion that cynicism is person focused either services recipient or management personnel and disengagement is work focused.

D. Turnover Intentions

Turnover intention among the employees is one of the variables of this study. Turnover intention is an important predicament for the organizations because sometimes it produces very costly results. "When turnover went down organizational performance increased (Halbrook, Meder, Stuchlik and Thorpe 1991). "This leads to a reduction in costs associated with retraining and hiring. In addition, decreased turnover lead to lower organizational costs for new employee lower productivity, time needed to train and support the new employee and mentoring time by current employees" (Cascio, 2010).

Employee turnover is heavily studied phenomenon in organizational perspective and particularly in services organizations. The research scholars on management and organizational behavior started to work on turnover intentions from 1950. Huge amount of literature is available on the causes and consequences of voluntary and involuntary employee turnover. It is explained in different ways "it is viewed as a voluntary separation of individual from organization" (Price and Mueller, 1981). "It results from a combination of organizational events, working conditions, and psychological factors

interacting with each other to affect employee attitudes in and toward the organization" (Fang, 2001).

Turnover intention occurs when the employee seeks other employment. Turnover occurs when the employee separates from employment (Kim & Stoner, 2008). It is important to understand the work related situations that would cause an employee to leave their position (Kim & Stoner, 2008). Popular opinion of employees leaving their jobs is due to dissatisfaction and/or better opportunities with another organization. Mitchell, Lee, Sablynski, and Erez (2001) suggest that there is more to the employee's decision to leave employment than simply dissatisfaction and other opportunities. Their construct of job embeddedness suggests that employees have multiple considerations to make prior to separation from employment. These considerations are on both personal and professional planes but are intertwined.

Turnover is a costly event for the organization as time and money have to be devoted to recruiting and training new employees. Turnover can be burdensome to existing employees as they are left to assume job duties and responsibilities of open positions until the new employee is trained (Templeton & Satcher, 2007). Additionally, service provision may suffer during the interim (Kim & Stoner, 2008).

Aarons, Sommerfeld, Hect, Silovshy, and Chaffin (2009) studied the effects of turnover on organizations that provide human services in community settings. They found turnover intention to be a predictor of a turnover. Turnover intention is classified as a withdrawal behavior similar to that of absenteeism and tardiness. Employees experiencing turnover intention are actively seeking another job and are less involved in current duties and responsibilities.

Turnover negatively affects remaining employees. Staff morale is lower and service provision is negatively impacted. Staff was ineffective as their productivity was lower than prior to turnover. Work teams were deficient as their workload was higher. Services were inconsistent due to the weakened relationship between the provider and service recipient. Finally, the financial implication of turnover was realized in the monetary cost

associated with training new staff (Aarons et al, 2009).

E. Relationship of Work Engagement, Burnout and Turnover Intentions

Maslach and Leiter (1997) are of opinion and their findings are suggesting that work engagement is totally concerned with the level of energy that is being used to complete the work, the level of involvement that is being shown in the work and how much efficiency is shown in the work. According to their study as far as burnout is concerned all above mentioned factors work exactly opposite to what is required for work engagement. (Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzlez-Roma, and Bakker, 2002) consider few other factors like dedicational approach that is being used and how much absorbing a person is. Perhaps the most important message from a study of burnout and engagement from within a framework of the areas of work life is that burnout and engagement do not occur in isolation, with a finite and predictable number of correlates or as a result of individual worker attributes (Leiter and Maslach, 2004). The turnover intention in this conceptual framework is considered as the withdrawal behavior of the individual to the organization and looking for job possibilities in other organizations (Moore, 2000; Blau 2007, Blau et. al. 2003). Saks (2006) found that “work engagement is positively and significantly related with employees’ job satisfaction and have significant and negative relations with turnover intention” (Saks, 2006). Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) also demonstrated that “work engagement influences turnover intention by mediating the relationship with job resources” (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004). “Previous research on engagement has found significant negative relationships between engagement and turnover intention” (Hallberg and Schaufeli, 2006). The literature regarding the relationship of job burnout and turnover intention is not consistent and plentiful. The symptoms of burnout are followed by symptoms of turnover intentions. “Burnout has also been found to be the dominant predictor of depression and depression has been proven to predict turnover intentions” (Anderson, 2008). While defining theoretical frameworks of burnout Cordes and Dougherty (1993), Demerouti

(2001) concluded “burnout is a key mediator of the relationship between chronic job stressors and various attitudinal outcomes” (Demerouti 2001). “Among these outcomes one is turnover intention, which has been empirically supported as a key outcome of burnout by several studies” (Harrington et al., 2001); (Huang, Chuang, and Lin, 2003).

IV. Mediation Model

Burnout has been found to contribute to the intent of employees to leave their organizations and it has been well documented by two Australian studies (Lingard, 2003; Sims, 2007); the later study suggested cynicism and emotional exhaustion as significant predictors of turnover intentions (Sims, 2007). Rothmann and Joubert (2007) reported similar findings in a South African study and Knudsen, Ducharme and Roman (2006) confirmed a positive link between emotional exhaustion and intentions to quit in a study conducted on a sample of therapeutic counselors. (Fogarty, Singh, Rhoads, and Moore, 2000). But no such study is found in literature that describes the mediation of work engagement between two dimensions of job burnout and turnover intentions. The currents study will fill this gap in the literature. The following mediation model is proposed for the study on the faculty of higher education institutions.

Figure 1:Mediation Model (c)

Independent variable
Depended variable

Mediating variable

Hypotheses

H1= There is negative relationship between dimensions of work engagement and burnout among faculty of higher education institutions.

H2= There is negative relationship between burnout, turnover intentions and work engagement.

H3= The work engagement mediates the relationship between dimension of burnout (emotional exhaustion, cynicism) and turnover intentions among the faculty of higher education institutions.

V. Methodology

The literature in the preceding chapters provides evidence that the research regarding the work engagement, job burnout and turnover intention in the higher education institutions perspective in Pakistan in general and Sindh in particular are very limited. Few scattered studies are available and published in relatively unknown journals.

F. Sample

The population for this study comprised faculty members of higher education institutions employing approximately 100 or more than 100 faculty members. All the male and female faculty members working in different departments are included in the sample of the study. In this study, convenient sampling method applied to collect the data. The faculty members briefed about nature and importance of study, questionnaire items and the process of data collection. The questionnaire distributed during the workdays at higher education institutions. The purpose for completing the research questionnaires and the procedure explained to the faculty members. Furthermore, for the ethical consideration, respondents were briefed that all data will be kept confidential and results will only be used for the academic research. The data was collected from 886 faculty members from higher education institutions at a response rate of over 66%.

G. Instruments

Engagement was assessed with the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES; Schaufeli and Bakker, 2003). Several studies have shown that the UWES has good psychometric properties” (Schaufeli and Bakker, 2004; Schaufeli, Salanova, Gonzalez Roma and Bakker, 2002). The instrument to assess work

engagement contain “three dimensions of work engagement e.g. vigor (being highly energetic during work), dedication (feeling proud in doing significant contribution to organization) and absorption (being highly involved in the work unaware of everything around)” (Schaufeli et al., 2003). In this study, the MBI-GS is applied Maslach and Leiter (1997) to assess the level of burnout among the faculty of higher education institutions in Sindh. On the numerous occasions Schaufeli (1998) has confirmed, “The most repeatedly used instrument for assessing burnout in diverse professions and organizations is Maslach Burnout Inventory general survey (MBI-GS)”. The key dimensions of MBI-GS include five items, Emotional exhaustion (feeling of being emotionally depleted and feeling stress during work). Six items Cynicism (distant attitude towards work and the people one works with). Five items Professional efficacy (negative evaluation of achievements at work). The items from the Nissly and colleagues (2005) turnover intention scale for the measurement of turnover intentions among the faculty of higher education institutions.

VI. Result

Table 1: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	648	73%
Female	239	27%
Total	887	100.0

The respondents for the study were both male and female faculty members of higher education institutions in Sindh. 73% respondents were male faculty members and 27% respondents were female faculty members from selected higher education institutions in Sindh.

Table 2: Experience of the Respondents

Experience	Frequency	Percent
Below Five Years	142	16%
5 to 10 Years	254	29%
10 To 15 Years	293	33%
15 To 20 Years	143	16%
Above 20 Years	55	6%
Total	887	100.0

The respondents from selected universities were segmented on the basis of experience in years. 16% of the respondents had below five years experience, 29% had five to ten years, 33% were having ten to fifteen years work experience, 16% of the respondents had fifteen to twenty years experience and 6% of the faculty members of the selected higher education institutions in Sindh had above twenty years experience of working at universities.

H. Correlation

The correlation coefficients have been calculated to find out and comprehend the level of relationship between the dimensions of work engagement, burnout and turnover intentions among faculty of higher education institutions. The purpose of calculating the correlation is to understand that to what extent the dimensions of study variables are related with each other.

Table 3: Mean and Correlation among Study Variables

V	Vg	Ab	Dd	Ex	Cy	TI
Vg	1	.63**	.61*	-.51**	-.49**	-.46**
Ab		1	.63*	.61**	-.51**	.37**
Dd			1	-.57**	-.50**	-.49**
Ex				1	-.57**	.36**
Cy					1	.66**
Ef						-.41**
TI						1

Vg= Vigor, Dd= Dedication, Ab= Absorption, Ex= Emotional Exhaustion, Cy= Cynicism, TI= Turnover Intentions

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

It can be observed from the correlation table that all the dimensions of work engagement among faculty of selected universities are significantly associated with each other. As the vigor among the faculty members increase the dedication also increase at (r=.63, p< .01). The increase in the level of absorption among respondents results in the increase of vigor and dedication at (r=.61, p< .01) and (r=.70, p< .01) respectively. As proposed the dimensions of job burnout are negatively related with the dimensions of work engagement, as the emotional exhaustion increase the vigor among respondents significantly decrease at (r=-.52, p< .01), dedication at(r=-.47, p< .01) and interestingly the absorption positively and significantly related with emotional exhaustion at (r=.61, p< .01) Same is the case with the cynicism where if the respondent is cynical than his vigor, dedication, absorption decreases at (r= -.49, p< .01), (r= -.46, p< .01) and (r= -.50, p< .01) respectively. The turnover intention was negatively and significantly related with dimensions of work engagement, vigor at (r= -.46, p< .01), dedication (r= -.44, p< .01) and absorption at (r= -.49, p< .01), the two dimensions of burnout emotional exhaustion at (r=.60, p< .01) at cynicism at (r=.66, p< .01) were positively and significantly related with turnover intension.

VII. Testing for Mediation of work engagement between Burnout and Turnover Intentions

The procedure for testing for mediation, as described by Barron and Kenny (1986) is applied for testing the mediation on the proposed variables. Testing for mediation involves establishing four conditions:

- Turnover intentions (DV) are significantly related to burnout (IV) (Path c)
- Burnout (IV) is significantly related to work engagement (MV) (Path a)
- Work engagement is significantly related to turnover intention (Path b)

- When controlling for the effects of MV on the DV, the effects of the IV on DV (Path c) is no longer significant.

Table 4: Analysis of (Path c)

Variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	β	Sig
Emotional Exhaustion	.70	.50	.49	.32	.000
Cynicism				.46	.000

Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention

The results of regression analysis shows that (R²= .50) 50% variation in the turnover intentions of the faculty members of higher education institutions of Sindh is the result of level burnout among them. The dimension of burnout, emotional exhaustion account for (β = .32) 32% positive and significant variation and cynicism (β= .46) account for 46% variation in the turnover intentions of the faculty. There results (r= .70) also explain the strong positive and significant relationship between the dependent variable and independent variable. The first condition regarding the (path c) suggested by Barron and Kenny (1986) has been met.

Table 5: Analysis Two (Path a)

Variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	β	Sig
Emotional Exhaustion	.64	.41	.40	-.40	.000
Cynicism				-.30	.000

Dependent Variable: Work Engagement

The result of regression analysis (r= .64) shows that there is strong relationship between work engagement and burnout. 41% variation in the work engagement is due to level of burnout among the faculty members of higher education institutions. The emotional exhaustion dimension of burnout account for (β= -.40) 40% negative and significant variation and cynicism (β=-.30) account for 30% variation in the level of work engagement of the faculty. The second condition regarding the (path

a) as suggested by Barron and Kenny (1986) have been fulfilled.

Table 6: Analysis (Path b)

Variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	β	Sig
Work Engagement	.53	.28	.28	-.53	.000

Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention

For the third condition, the regression was applied on the turnover intention as dependent variable and work engagement as independent variable. The (r= .53) show that there is moderate relationship between the dependent and independent variables. (R²= .28) portray that 28% variation in the turnover intentions of the faculty is caused by work engagement. The (β= -.53) indicates that there is negative significant relationship between work engagement and turnover intentions. The result explains that the third condition for the mediation has also been fulfilled.

Table 7: Mediation Analysis

Variable	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	β	Sig
Model I	.70	.50	.49		
Emotional Exhaustion				.32	
Cynicism				.46	.000
Model II	.71	.51	.50		.000
Emotional Exhaustion				.26	.000
Cynicism				.41	.000
Wok Engagement				-.14	.001

Dependent Variable: Turnover Intention

The regression results describe that at step two the work engagement is significantly and negatively related with turnover intention. The (β = .32) for emotional exhaustion in the model one signify that it brought 32% variation in the turnover intention and (β = .46) explains that cynicism account for 46% change in the turnover intention. In the second

model, the ($\beta = .26$) and ($\beta = .41$) for emotional exhaustion and cynicism has considerably reduced due to inclusion of mediating variable, work engagement. The β values for the controlled regulations path c which was significant in the analysis one is still significant while controlling for the effects of work engagement. Hence, the final condition suggested by Barron and Kenny (1986) has not been completely fulfilled. However, the relationship among the variable is significant at .01 level. So it can be concluded that work engagement partially mediate between burnout and turnover intentions. The mediation results show that work engagement is partially mediate between job burnout and turnover intentions so hypothesis of the study is partially supported.

VIII. Discussion and Conclusion

The mediation of work engagement between job burnout and turnover intentions of faculty of different higher education institutions in Sindh was tested by using Barron and Kenny (1986) process. The regression was applied on the four step process of mediation. The mediation was tested on work engagement, two dimensions of burnout (emotional exhaustion, cynicism) and turnover intention. In the first regression the dimensions of burnout e.g. emotional exhaustion ($\beta = .32$, $p < .01$) and cynicism ($\beta = .46$, $p < .01$) were positively and significantly predicting the turnover intentions among the faculty. The result shows that if the faculty is emotionally exhausted and develop cynical attitude than they contemplate to find another job. The dimensions of burnout are also negatively and significantly predicting the work engagement among the faculty of universities. Simultaneously, the work engagement is also significantly and negatively predicting the turnover intentions of faculty. The above results support the mediation conditions of Barron and Kenny (1986). The regression results of mediation show that the two dimensions of burnout ($\beta = .32$, $p < .01$) for emotional exhaustion and ($\beta = .46$, $p < .01$) in model I were reduced to ($\beta = .26$, $p < .01$) and ($\beta = .41$, $p < .01$) in model II after the inclusion of work engagement ($\beta = -.14$, $p < .01$). All the variables are significant in the final model and do not meet the final condition for mediation Barron and Kenny (1986). Same results are reported by

Koyuncu et al. (2006); Saks (2006); and Schaufeli and Bakker (2004). In a study of Sims (2007) in Australia also suggested that the emotional exhaustion and cynicism is the predictor of turnover intention. This study has also concluded that work engagement is reducing the impact of burnout (emotional exhaustion, cynicism) on the turnover intentions. The mediation between the dimensions of burnout and turnover intentions is partially mediated by work engagement. The results of this study in terms of mediation of work engagement between burnout dimensions and turnover intentions are exceptional and can be tested further. The tendency of work engagement to mediate relationships between burnout and turnover intentions among faculty are only to partial extent that may point out to the possibility of multiple variables in higher education institutions perspective mediate the relationship. The results of this study provide comprehensive evidence to interpret the relationship between the work engagement, burnout and turnover intentions among the faculty which will broaden the horizon of occupational psychology research in Pakistan.

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